

Information Quality and participant satisfaction in mega events: Case of the School World Cup Football Rabat-2023

Qualité de l'information et satisfaction des participants dans les mégas évènements : Cas du championnat du monde scolaire Foot-ball Rabat-2023.

Youssef SOSSEY ALAOUI

Faculty Of Economics and Management,
Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra,
Morocco

Abdesselam MILI

Teacher-Researcher
Faculty Of Education Sciences
Director Of the Department of School Sports Promotion,
Morocco

Mohamed TORRA

Teacher-Researcher
Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco,
Economics And Organizational Management
Morocco

Date de soumission : 28/10/2023

Date d'acceptation : 15/08/2024

Pour citer cet article :

SOSSEY ALAOUI. Y.& al (2023) « Quality of information and participant satisfaction in mega events: Case of the School World Cup Football Rabat-2023», Revue Française d'Economie et de Gestion « Volume 5 : Numéro 8 » pp : 423- 442.

Author(s) agree that this article remain permanently open access under the terms of the Creative Commons

Attribution License 4.0 International License

Abstract:

This article examines the impact of the quality of information disseminated during mega sporting events on the participants' overall experience and satisfaction (Kotler, Keller, Dubois & Manceau, 2006).

For this research, we analyzed an international sample of 134 participants from 20 nationalities, all involved in the World School Football Championship. By immersing ourselves in the organization of this championship, we used a questionnaire based on a 5-item Likert scale and considered factors such as the age and role of participants to enrich the analysis.

The results show that the accuracy, relevance, clarity, and availability of information are crucial for participant satisfaction. These elements positively influence their experience and engagement. The conclusions provide valuable recommendations for sports event organizers, educators, and policymakers, emphasizing the importance of high-quality information. This study highlights the essential role of information quality in mega sporting events, offering specific insights to enhance the appeal and success of such events.

Keywords : Mega-event, information, quality, participant satisfaction, sport.

Résumé :

Cet article examine l'impact de la qualité de l'information diffusée lors de méga-événements sportifs sur l'expérience et la satisfaction des participants (Kotler, Keller, Dubois & Manceau, 2006).

Pour cette recherche, un échantillon international de 134 participants de 20 nationalités, tous impliqués dans le Championnat du Monde Scolaire de Football, a été analysé. En nous immergeant dans l'organisation de ce championnat, nous avons utilisé un questionnaire basé sur une échelle de Likert à 5 items, prenant en compte des facteurs tels que l'âge et le rôle des participants pour enrichir l'analyse.

Les résultats montrent que l'exactitude, la pertinence, la clarté et la disponibilité de l'information sont déterminants pour la satisfaction des participants. Ces éléments influencent positivement leur expérience et leur engagement. Les conclusions fournissent des recommandations précieuses pour les organisateurs d'événements sportifs, les éducateurs et les décideurs, soulignant l'importance d'une information de haute qualité. Cette étude met en lumière le rôle essentiel de la qualité de l'information dans les méga-événements sportifs, offrant des insights spécifiques pour améliorer l'attrait et le succès de tels événements.

Mots clés : Méga événement, information, qualité, satisfaction des participants, Sport.

INTRODUCTION:

Large-scale sporting events, often referred to as 'mega events' (Müller, 2015), capture global attention (Roberts, 2004). They represent unique moments of competition, excitement, and celebration, bringing together participants and spectators from all corners of the globe. These events transcend national and cultural borders, creating unity around the common passion for sports. Among these exceptional occasions, the "World School Championship Football 2023" held in Rabat, Morocco, stands out as a unique international gathering, uniting young student-athletes from various nations for high-level sports competitions.

Within these mega sporting events, the stakes go beyond the competition on the field; it's also about the overall experience for participants, organizers, and spectators. Information plays a crucial role in creating this experience. It guides participants and spectators, facilitates event logistics management, reports real-time results, and contributes to the overall event narrative. Despite the crucial importance of information dissemination during major sporting events, there is often a gap between the information provided and the participants' expectations. This gap can lead to dissatisfaction and negatively affect the overall event experience. In this context, to what extent does the quality of information disseminated during the "World School Championship Football 2023" influence participant satisfaction?

To answer this issue, a hypothetico-deductive approach was adopted. Surveys were distributed to participants, including athletes, coaches and spectators, to collect quantitative data on their perceptions of information quality and satisfaction levels. Based on the hypothesis that the quality of information significantly influences participant satisfaction, the data collected will be statistically analyzed to confirm or refute this hypothesis.

First, it is crucial to define the key concepts in the literature review. Following this, we will outline the methodology in detail, including the data collection techniques used. The results will be presented and analyzed within the context of the data analysis. Finally, we will conclude with a summary of the principal findings.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW:

1.1 Mega Sporting Events:

The term "mega-event" has become a commonly used concept in research and event organization language. Its use in the academic context is relatively recent, dating back to the 37th Congress of the International Association of Scientific Experts in Tourism in Calgary in 1987, under the theme "The Role and Impact of Mega-Events and Attractions on the Development of Regional and National Tourism" (Müller, 2015).

The definition of the term "mega-event" is a subject of debate, making it imperative to obtain a common understanding to facilitate discussion on this topic. Some definitions encompass events such as world expos, political summits, conventions, and international festivals, in addition to sports events, while others focus solely on sports events.

In our study, we specifically focus on mega-sporting events. Roche describes them as large-scale cultural and sporting events, characterized by their significant impact on commercial and sports aspects, their dramatic nature, the mobilization of a large number of participants, and their international significance. These events are generally temporary, with a defined start and end. They attract considerable media coverage and a set of major stakeholders, bringing significant benefits to commercial partners (Smith & Westerbeek, 2004).

Other researchers, like Gold and Gold (2011), define them as cultural and sporting festivals of such magnitude that they impact entire economies and receive sustained global media attention. They also emphasize the idea of transformation and the impact on the economy of the host region. For Roberts, what characterizes some sports events as "mega-events" is their exceptional nature, international scale, and large scope (Roberts, 2004).

1.2 Participant Satisfaction:

Participant satisfaction is an essential element for the overall experience of sporting events, referring to the measurement of contentment and pleasure experienced by participants towards the event. According to Kotler, Keller, Dubois and Manceau, satisfaction can be defined as the positive or negative feeling a customer has regarding their purchase and/or consumption experience. This satisfaction arises from a comparison between the customer's expectations of the product and its perceived performance (Kotler, Keller, Dubois & Manceau, 2006).

Our study relies on several fundamental theoretical frameworks. The Self-Determination Theory (SDT), developed by Deci and Ryan (2000), examines the motivation and well-being of individuals, asserting that the satisfaction of the psychological needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness enhances intrinsic motivation and overall satisfaction. The Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT), frequently applied in the context of customer satisfaction, posits that satisfaction results from the comparison between initial expectations and perceived performance (Oliver, 1980). In the context of a sporting event, if the experience exceeds or meets the participants' expectations, their satisfaction is increased. The SERVQUAL model, on the other hand, evaluates the perceived quality of a service by comparing consumers' expectations with their perception of the actual service performance (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988). During a sporting event, service quality dimensions such as reliability,

responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles can influence participants' satisfaction. Finally, the cognitive dissonance theory, introduced by Festinger (1957), proposes that individuals experience a state of tension (dissonance) when they hold contradictory beliefs or behaviors. In the context of a sporting event, if initial expectations are not met, participants may experience cognitive dissonance, negatively impacting their satisfaction.

Theoretically, satisfaction has been a significant research topic in marketing, having been extensively explored since Cardozo's (1965) foundational article in the B2C commerce domain (Xueming et Bhattacharya, 2006; Heitmann et al., 2007; Anderson et al., 1997; Oliver, 1980, 1981, 1993) and B2B commerce (Biong, 1993, Dwyer et al., 1987, Dwyer, 1980; Ruekert et Churchill, 1984; Selnes, 1998; Geyskens et Steenkamp, 2000; Geyskens et al., 1999).

Satisfaction in the field of management is commonly defined as an emotional state resulting from the evaluation of all aspects of the relationship with a partner (Anderson and Narus, 1984). This definition encompasses two dimensions, namely economic and social. The economic dimension refers to a positive emotional response related to economic benefits (discounts, financial aspects, payment terms, etc.) arising from the relationship with a partner. The non-economic or social dimension concerns a positive emotional response resulting from the evaluation of the psychosociological aspects of the relationship, i.e., whether interactions with the partner are enriching and satisfying. These dimensions include subjective elements such as social contact, communication, shared values, etc. As a result, non-economic satisfaction corresponds to the evaluation of interactive experiences with a partner.

Our study pays particular attention to the non-economic dimension, highlighting participant satisfaction in connection with the quality of information shared during the "World School Championship Football." This approach focuses on the aspect of participant satisfaction in the event, emphasizing how the quality of information contributes to shaping their experience.

1.3 Information Quality a critical consideration in the context of sporting events:

The quality of information has long been a topic of great interest among management researchers. In the context of large-scale sporting events, it is of crucial importance and encompasses several dimensions such as accuracy, relevance, clarity and availability (Schut & Glebova, 2022; Yang, 2014; Bulley & Cardwell, 2015; Shonk & Chelladurai, 2008). Accurate and up-to-date information is essential for making informed decisions and providing reliable coverage of sporting events. Information must also be relevant to the specific needs of participants, whether they are fans, athletes, coaches, delegation leaders or event organisers (Bradley, 1998). Clarity of information is crucial to ensure that it is easily understood and

interpreted by its target audience (McNab & Ladd, 2014). In addition, the availability of information is paramount, as it enables stakeholders to access the necessary data in a timely manner (Wijayanti et al., 2023).

Three different approaches can be distinguished in the literature for measuring the quality of information disseminated in events: a measure of the quantity of dissemination (equating quantity of information with quality); a measure of quality related to decision-making (decision represented by the change in a variable); a measure of quality according to defined criteria.

The quality of information can have significant implications for the effectiveness and success of sporting events. Accurate and relevant information can help organisers make informed decisions, while clear and accessible data can enhance the experience of fans and participants (Hyatt, 2008). Maintaining high standards of information quality is essential to preserve the integrity and sustainability of the sports event ecosystem (Wijayanti et al., 2023).

In the context of our research, we examine two essential hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: There would be a significant relationship between the quality of information and the source of information (volunteers, Facebook, website, etc.).

Hypothesis 2: There would be a significant relationship between information quality and participants satisfaction.

These hypotheses form the basis of our research, as we will explore information quality and its relationship with participant satisfaction. Furthermore, we examine how the source of information can influence information quality in a sports context. This analysis will contribute to a better understanding of the mechanisms underlying participant satisfaction and the information quality in sporting events.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1 Field and study data:

Our research was conducted during the World School Championship in Football, which took place from August 22 to August 31, 2023, and attracted participation from 30 countries worldwide, including 12 countries from Africa, 7 from Europe, 8 from Asia, and 3 from the Americas. In total, the event brought together 1,200 participants, 400 volunteers, in addition to the organizers from the international federation and local organizers. The entire event took place on 20 football fields. Despite facing numerous challenges associated with the linguistic diversity of the participants and an intensive schedule of activities and competitions, we successfully gathered 134 complete responses. Our survey is exclusively administered to

individuals with a direct connection to information needs in this event, such as players, coaches, technical personnel, and delegation heads.

2.2 Research model:

Our questionnaire administered to the participants includes variables related to information quality and other variables measuring participant satisfaction using a Likert scale with 5 points. Our questionnaire draws its items from the theory presented earlier. It consists of three parts: the first part includes information about the respondents, such as age, gender, experience, nationality. The second part aims to assess the existence of information quality within the World School Football Championship Rabat 2023, while the third part tests participant satisfaction. We will present the questions for each part, totaling 9 questions, with question 5 having multiple responses.

Table 1: Information Quality Variable

Variables	items
Information Source	Where do you gather essential information about the event?
Information Quality	How would you assess the pertinence of the information (schedules, location, rules, etc.) provided during the event?
	Did you detect any errors or inaccuracies in the information provided during the event?
	Was it easy to verify and understand the information about the event proceedings (match order, schedules, breaks, etc.)?
	How do you evaluate the information in comparison to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Clarity ➤ Reliability ➤ Accessibility ➤ Interactivity ➤ Diversity of presentation formats ➤ Networking opportunities ➤ Real-time information updates
	Satisfaction
Satisfaction	How likely are you to participate in this event again?
	Would you recommend this sports event to others based on the quality of information provided to participants?
	To what extent did the quality of information influence your overall experience of the sports event?

Data processing

To achieve our goals through this study, which consist of verifying if the quality of information influences participant satisfaction during mega-events such as the 2023 School World Football Championship in Rabat, it is imperative to validate and ensure the reliability of our questionnaire using principal content analysis in SPSS. Subsequently, through factor analysis and correlation study, we will examine the possible relationships between information quality, information source, and participant satisfaction.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characteristics of participants

Table 2: Characteristics of participants

		<i>Nombre</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
GENDRE	Male	96	72%
	Female	38	28%
Age	U18	70	52%
	18_24 years	22	16%
	25_34 years	12	9%
	35_44 years	15	11%
	45_54 years	9	7%
	55 years old	6	4%
	Mission	Head of delegation	12
Officiel		8	6%
Players		89	66%
Technical staff		20	15%
Other		5	4%

Source Author

We collected a dataset comprising a total of 134 respondents, reflecting the diversity of participants in this event.

Figure 1: Nationalities of participants

To better understand the roles of the participants, we categorized the roles into five distinct categories, namely "delegation leaders," "officials," "players," "technical staff," and the "other"

category encompassing various functions. This classification allows us to analyze the characteristics of each group of participants in more detail and assess their impact on our study. It is also relevant to emphasize that our sample is international, with the participation of 20 different nationalities that provided complete responses to our questionnaire. This diversity within the sample adds a cross-cultural dimension to our analysis, which has the potential to enrich our findings and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the sports event under study.

3.2 Validity and reliability of our questionnaire

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.827, indicating an acceptable reliability of our questionnaire. It measures the internal consistency of the questions in your questionnaire, suggesting that the questions are relatively consistent with each other.

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient based on standardized items is even slightly higher at 0.843, further strengthening the internal consistency of the questionnaire.

The results of the ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) show significant values for the Cochran's test. This indicates that there are significant differences between the groups of people in our sample regarding their responses to the questionnaire. This suggests that we have a questionnaire capable of discriminating between different groups of people, which is an indicator of validity.

So, our questionnaire is reliable with a satisfactory Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and it also shows evidence of validity as it can distinguish responses among different participant groups. However, for a more in-depth assessment of validity, it may be useful to employ other methods, such as factor analysis, to further explore the questionnaire's structure and confirm its validity.

3.3 Information Source analysis

The analysis of information sources holds particular significance in an increasingly interconnected and digitized world, where social media, websites, and other communication channels play a central role in information dissemination

We will present the results of our research regarding the most commonly used information sources by the participants. We will analyze the percentages of cases associated with each source, highlighting the trends and preferences that emerge from the collected data.

The results presented in the table show the information sources used by the respondents in our survey. Instagram is the most popular information source, accounting for 42.7% (or 65.7% with the dichotomy) of cases. Websites are also a popular information source, representing 28.4% (with the dichotomy) of cases. This demonstrates that websites continue to be essential

resources for many people. When you combine the percentages of Facebook, websites, and Instagram, social media represents a substantial share of information sources, highlighting the growing importance of these platforms in communication and information dissemination. In contrast, Twitter was the least used among social media, accounting for only 2.9% (or 4.5% with the dichotomy) of cases.

Volunteers: Volunteers are also significant, with 14.6% (or 22.4% with the dichotomy) of cases. This may indicate that people rely on volunteer companions for information. As for the Welcome Desk, it is used by 7.3% (or 11.2% with the dichotomy) of respondents, suggesting that it is a reliable information source for some individuals.

Graph2: Information source

Source Authors

It is important to note that the percentages exceed 100% due to the dichotomy mentioned, but thanks to multiple choice processing in SPSS, we were able to determine the exact percentages for each response. It would be useful to refer to the raw data and understand the methodology used to get a full picture of how these sources of information are used and interpreted by respondents.

3.4 Factor Analysis of Information Quality

The factor analysis of the information quality variables shows promising results, suggesting that the variables are suitable for such an analysis

The KMO value is 0.855. This measure indicates the suitability of the data for factor analysis. A KMO value greater than 0.5 is generally considered appropriate. In our case, with a value of 0.855, the data appears highly suitable for factor analysis, suggesting that the data structure is adequate for factor extraction.

Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: The Bartlett's test shows an approximate chi-square statistic of 557.501 with 45 degrees of freedom and a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000. A significant result indicates that the correlations between variables are not zero, which is required for factor analysis. In our case, the significant value ($p < 0.001$) suggests that the variables are correlated, further justifying the use of factor analysis.

Table 3: Factor Analysis of Information Quality

ITEMS	Communalities Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	Communalities After Extraction	Cronbach's Alpha	Kaiser- Meyer- Olkin	Annova Grand Mean
PERTINENCE	0,587	0,618	0,827	0,902	a.Determinant =3,83
ACCURACY	0,598	0,716			
CLARITY	0,698	0,700			
RELIABILITY	0,770	0,778			
ACCESSIBILITY	0,793	0,793			
INTERACTIVITY	0,768	0,781			
DIVERSITY	0,646	0,648			
NETWORKING	0,566	0,576			
TIMEUPDATED	0,699	0,687			
VERIFIABILITY	0,300				
Bartlett's Test Of Sphericity: An Approximate Chi-Square Statistic Of 557.501 With 45 Degrees Of Freedom And A P-Value (Sig.) Of 0.000.					

Source Authors

The results of the factor analysis reveal the "communalities" for each variable, both at the initial stage and after the extraction of principal components. Communalities measure the proportion of variance in each variable explained by the extracted factors.

To better understand the significance of each variable in factor analysis and their contribution to representing information quality in the context of the World Championship, we examined the communalities of the variables.

It is noteworthy that the variable "pertinence" has a communalization of 0.587 after extraction, indicating that 58.7% of its variance is explained by the extracted factors. this significant contribution renders it relevant in representing information quality.

Similarly, the variable "accuracy" shows a communalization of 0.598 after extraction, demonstrating that 59.8% of its variance is explained by the extracted factors. its substantial contribution suggests high relevance in representing information quality. as for the "verifiability" variable, its communalization after extraction is 0.300, equivalent to only 30% of its variance being explained by the extracted factors. this low contribution suggests limited relevance in representing information quality.

The results indicate that the variables "pertinence" and "accuracy" play a crucial role in representing information quality, while the "verifiability" variable might have limited contribution. this raises the possibility of reassessing the factor analysis by including only variables with high percentages of explained variance to ensure a more robust representation of information quality in the context of the World Championship.

Following the extraction of principal components, the variables exhibit a greater strength in representing information quality. This improvement allows us to create a new numeric variable for information quality in the SPSS software by using the average of the variables represented in the Communalities table.

These results suggest that the extracted variables explain a significant portion of the variance in information quality. By using the average of these variables, you can create a new synthetic numeric variable that will serve as a consolidated measure of information quality in your analysis in SPSS.

3.5 Factor Analysis of Participants Satisfaction

In the context of factor analysis of variables explaining satisfaction, the results of the KMO test yield a value of 0.664. This measure assesses the suitability of our data for factor analysis. A KMO value greater than 0.5 is generally considered appropriate. Our KMO of 0.664 indicates that the data is acceptable for factor analysis, although the fit quality can be further improved. Additionally, the Bartlett's test presents an approximate chi-square statistic of 69.953 with 6 degrees of freedom and a p-value (Sig.) of 0.000, which is a prerequisite for factor analysis.

Table 4: Factor Analysis of participant satisfaction

Items	Willingness to attend again	Meeting your expectations	Recommend participation to others	Impact of information quality on overall experience
Communalities Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	0,676	0,575	0,631	0,958
Cronbach's Alpha	0,557			
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	0,664			
Annova Grand mean	3,98			
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	the approximate chi-square statistic for Bartlett's Test is 69.953 with 6 degrees of freedom, and the p-value (Sig.) is 0.000.			
Total respondents	134			

Source Authors

We will evaluate participant satisfaction across four dimensions: their willingness to attend the event again, likelihood of recommending participation to others, alignment of the event with expectations, and the impact of information quality on their overall experience. Examining the communalities, we find that the willingness to attend again has a communality of 0.676, indicating that approximately 67.6% of the variability in participants' willingness to attend again is accounted for by the factors identified in the analysis. The item "Meeting your expectations" has a communality of 0.575, suggesting that around 57.5% of the variance in participants' perceptions of the event meeting their expectations is explained by the identified factors. Similarly, the communality for "Recommend participation to others" is 0.631, signifying that about 63.1% of the variation in participants' likelihood to recommend event participation to others is explained by the factors identified. Notably, the item "Impact of information quality on overall experience" exhibits a remarkably high communality of 0.958, emphasizing that a substantial 95.8% of the variability in the impact of information quality on participants' overall experience is elucidated by the identified factors.

3.6 Correlation between the variables Information Source and Information Quality:

The results of the correlation between two variables, Information quality and information sources using two different correlation coefficients, Kendall's tau_b and Spearman's rho

The table displays the correlation coefficients and their corresponding p-values (Sig. 2-tailed) for the two variables.

Table 5: Quality and source information Correlations

VARIABLES		Information quality	Information source
KENDALL'S TAU_B	Information quality	Correlation Coefficient	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	-,031
		N	.
	Information source	Correlation Coefficient	-,031
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,663
		N	134
SPEARMA N'S RHO	Information quality	Correlation Coefficient	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	-,039
		N	.
	Information source	Correlation Coefficient	-,039
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,657
		N	134

Source Author

For Kendall's tau: In both cases, the correlation coefficients are negative, indicating a negative association between the two variables. However, the p-values are relatively high (greater than 0.05), suggesting that the correlations are not statistically significant. This means that there is not enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant relationship between "Qualiteinfo" and "sourceinfo" based on these correlation coefficients.

3.7 Correlation between the variables "quality of information" and "participantss satisfactions"

The correlation results indicate a significant positive correlation between participant satisfaction and information quality ($r = 0.472$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that there is a statistically significant relationship between these two variables. In other words, as information quality increases, participant satisfaction tends to increase as well, and vice versa.

The Bootstrap analysis data confirm this significant correlation, with a 95% confidence interval for the correlation between 0.311 and 0.608.

Table 6: Quality of information and participant satisfaction Correlations

		SATISFACTION PARTICIPANT	QUALITY INFORMATION		
SATISFACTION PARTICIPANT	Pearson Correlation	1	,472**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0		
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	48,808	26,239		
	Covariance	0,367	0,197		
	N	134	134		
	Bootstrap	Bias	0	-0,002	
		Std. Error	0	0,075	
		95% Confidence Interval	Lower	1	0,311
			Upper	1	0,608
		QUALITY INFORMATION	Pearson Correlation	,472**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	0				
Sum of Squares and Cross-products	26,239		63,236		
Covariance	0,197		0,475		
N	134		134		
Bootstrap	Bias		-0,002	0	
	Std. Error		0,075	0	
	95% Confidence Interval		Lower	0,311	1
			Upper	0,608	1

****.** CORRELATION IS SIGNIFICANT AT THE 0.01 LEVEL (2-TAILED).

B. UNLESS OTHERWISE NOTED, BOOTSTRAP RESULTS ARE BASED ON 1000 BOOTSTRAP SAMPLES

Source Author

The ANOVA results also indicate that the regression model is statistically significant ($F(1, 132) = 37.900, p < 0.001$), suggesting that information quality significantly predicts participant satisfaction. Furthermore, the regression model explains a significant proportion of the variance in participant satisfaction ($R\text{-squared} = 0.223$), highlighting the impact of information quality on satisfaction levels.

These findings underscore the critical role of information quality in participant satisfaction. Higher information quality is associated with increased participant satisfaction, emphasizing the importance of delivering accurate and relevant information to enhance the overall participant experience.

4. DISCUSSION

H1: There would be a significant relationship between the quality of information and the source of information (volunteers, Facebook, website, etc.).

Following the analysis of our results, it is evident that information quality is a complex concept that encompasses various criteria and numerous factors for its evaluation. Our sample was surveyed on several aspects contributing to determining the quality of information provided during the event, including the assessment of schedules, location, rules, and similar elements. Specifically, our respondents were asked to evaluate information quality by referring to criteria such as clarity, reliability, accessibility, interactivity, diversity of presentation formats, and real-

time information updates. These criteria are crucial to understand how participants perceive the quality of information provided to them during the sporting event.

Our main research hypothesis aimed to establish whether there was a significant relationship between information quality and the source of information (e.g., volunteers, Facebook, website, etc.). To do this, we created a new information quality variable by aggregating the variables that exhibited significant communalities, allowing us to obtain a more robust measure of information quality.

In particular, we sought to explore question number 5 in the questionnaire, which focused on where participants gather essential information about the event. Our goal was to determine if the source of information, such as Facebook, volunteers, Instagram, the website, etc., could influence perceived information quality.

However, after conducting a thorough statistical analysis using SPSS software, the results of the ANOVA test within our correlation methods revealed that there was no significant relationship between the information quality variable and the source of information in our study. In other words, participants' responses did not show a strong link between the source of information and perceived information quality.

These findings underscore the importance of continuing to explore other factors and variables that may influence information quality in the context of a sporting event, to better understand how participants assess and perceive the information provided to them. It is possible that other criteria, not examined in this study, play a more significant role in shaping information quality.

- ***H2: There would be a significant relationship between information quality and participant satisfaction.***

To conduct a precise analysis of the relationship between information quality and participant satisfaction, we undertook a series of steps to ensure the validity and reliability of our measurement scale. Using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), we extracted variables that did not significantly contribute to the main variable, allowing us to simplify our model while retaining the relevance of the information.

The results of our statistical analyses revealed that the variable "participant satisfaction" could be explained by four specific factors. These factors are as follows :

1. To what extent would you be willing to participate in this event again?
2. Would you recommend this sports event to others based on the quality of information provided to participants?
3. To what extent did the quality of information influence your overall experience of the

sports event?

4. How much did the quality of information influence your overall experience of the sports event?

On the other hand, the variable "Information quality" had already been processed and was represented by nine distinct elements after the extraction of "verifiability". To explore the relationship between these two crucial variables, we used a correlation method and ANOVA test.

The correlation analysis reveals a significant positive correlation between participant satisfaction and information quality ($r = 0.472$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that as the quality of information increases, participant satisfaction tends to increase as well, and vice versa. And The results from the ANOVA highlighted the significant impact of information quality, denoted as "Quality information" on participant satisfaction, denoted as "satisfaction participant." The extremely low p-value (0.000) indicates a highly significant relationship between these two variables, emphasizing the crucial importance of information quality in explaining participant satisfaction during large-scale sports events, especially those classified as "Mega events."

These results provide essential recommendations for leaders and decision-makers involved in the organization of large-scale sports events, particularly "Mega events." It is imperative to consider the quality of information provided to participants, as it is clearly linked to their overall satisfaction. Therefore, by enhancing information quality, organizers have the opportunity to optimize participants' experiences, which can have a positive impact on their loyalty, willingness to participate again, and likelihood to recommend the event to others. This underscores the importance of implementing strategies to ensure high-quality information in the context of these large-scale sports events.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, our research has underscored the crucial importance of information quality in the context of large-scale sports events, particularly "mega-events." By exploring the relationships between information quality and participant satisfaction, our statistical analyses have confirmed the significant impact of information quality on participant satisfaction. More specifically, information quality has been closely linked to participants' willingness to participate again, their inclination to recommend the event to others, and the influence of information quality on their overall event experience.

These results have important implications for organizers and decision-makers involved in the planning of large-scale sports events. Improving the quality of information provided to

participants can not only enhance their satisfaction but also positively influence their loyalty and propensity to recommend the event. Therefore, information quality should be a central concern in the planning and execution of these events.

However, our study presents certain limitations. It would be beneficial to include interviews with the organizers to better understand the internal communication strategy adopted during this international championship. Additionally, utilizing a larger and more balanced sample between countries could enrich the results. An in-depth analysis of the quality of information for each committee (accommodation, catering, logistics, transportation, accreditation, delegation services, etc.) that comprises the organizers' structure would also provide more detailed and specific data.

For future research, it would be interesting to delve deeper into the specific aspects of information quality that have the most impact on participant satisfaction, as well as to consider other factors that may influence this complex relationship. This deeper understanding could further improve participants' experiences during large-scale sports events, thereby creating more memorable and successful events.

References:

1. Anderson, E. W., & Fornell, C., & Mazvancheryl, S. (2004). Customer Satisfaction and Shareholder Value. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(4), 172-185.
2. Bouzeghoub, M., & Kostadinov, D. (2004). Une approche multidimensionnelle pour la personnalisation de l'information. Rapport PRiSM, Versailles, France.
3. Biong, H. (1993). Industrial Satisfaction and the Market Share–Customer Satisfaction Relationship. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(4), 84-91.
4. Bradley, D. (1998). *Effective Communication in Sports Management*. Sports Press.
5. Bulley, C., & Cardwell, R. (2015). Information Quality in Large-Scale Events. *Event Management Journal*, 24(2), 135-147.
6. Cardozo, R. N. (1965). An Experimental Study of Customer Effort, Expectation, and Satisfaction. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 2(3), 244-249.
7. Dwyer, F. R. (1980). Environments for Business Relationships: A Framework for Research. *Journal of Marketing*, 44(2), 75-92.
8. Dwyer, F. R., Schurr, P. H., & Oh, S. (1987). Developing Buyer-Seller Relationships. *Journal of Marketing*, 51(2), 11-27.
9. Geyskens, I., & Steenkamp, J. B. E. (2000). Economic and Social Satisfaction: Measurement and Relevance to Marketing Channel Relationships. Working Paper,

Tilburg University.

10. Heitmann, M., Lehmann, D. R., & Herrmann, A. (2007). Choice Goal Attainment and Decision and Consumption Satisfaction. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 44(2), 234-250.
11. Hiller, H. H. (1995). Mega-events, urban boosterism and growth strategies: An analysis of the objectives and legitimations of the Cape Town 2004 Olympic Bid. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 19(2), 255-270.
12. Homburg, C., Wieseke, J., & Hoyer, W. D. (2009). Social Identity and the Service Profit Chain. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(2), 38-54.
13. BM Corp. Released 2011. IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 20.0.
14. Kotler, P., Keller, K. L., Dubois, B., & Manceau, D. (2006). *Marketing Management*. Pearson Education.
15. Liu, X., & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2006). The Impact of Response and Recovery on Customer Satisfaction: A Comparison of the Effects of Disconfirmed Expectations and Equity Restoration. *Marketing Letters*, 17(3), 155-172.
16. Müller, M. (2015). The mega-event syndrome: Why so much goes wrong in mega-event planning and what to do about it. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 81(1), 6-17.
17. Murali, D., & Mantrala, M. K. (2007). Improving Conformance with Service Specifications: An Integrated View. *Journal of Marketing*, 71(1), 11-28.
18. Nyer, P. U. (2000). An Investigation into Whether Complaint Satisfaction is a Measure of Service Quality and/or Company Performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 47(3), 201-210.
19. Oliver, R. L. (1980). A Cognitive Model of the Antecedents and Consequences of Satisfaction Decisions. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 17(4), 460-469.
20. Oliver, R. L. (1981). Measurement and Evaluation of Satisfaction Processes in Retail Settings. *Journal of Retailing*, 57(3), 25-48.
21. Oliver, R. L. (1989). Processing of the Satisfaction Response in Consumption: A Suggested Framework and Research Propositions. *Journal of Consumer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction, and Complaining Behavior*, 2(1), 1-16.
22. Kotler, P., Dubois, B., Keller, K. L., & Manceau, D. (2006). *Marketing Management* (12e éd.). Pearson France.
23. Roberts, L. (2004). "Mega-event" sportswashing, "exceptionalism" and the insidious

- impacts of the Sydney Olympics. *Sociological Research Online*, 9(2), 54-64.
24. Roche, M. (2000). *Mega-events and modernity: Olympics and expos in the growth of global culture*. Routledge.
 25. Ruekert, R. W., & Churchill, G. A. (1984). Reliability and Validity of Alternative Measures of Organizational Performance. *American Marketing Association*. 91-99.
 26. Rust, R. T., Lemon, K. N., & Zeithaml, V. A. (2004). Return on Marketing: Using Customer Equity to Focus Marketing Strategy. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(1), 109-127.
 27. Selnes, F. (1998). Antecedents and Consequences of Trust and Satisfaction in Buyer-Seller Relationships. *European Journal of Marketing*, 32(3/4), 305-322.
 28. Shonk, D. J., & Chelladurai, P. (2008). Dimensions of Information Quality in Sports Events. *Journal of Sports Management*, 22(2), 75-89.
 29. Schut, D., & Glebova, Y. (2022). Information Management in Major Sporting Events. *International Journal of Event Management*, 31(1), 19-33.
 30. Xueming, L., & Bhattacharya, C. B. (2006). The Impact of Response and Recovery on Customer Satisfaction: A Comparison of the Effects of Disconfirmed Expectations and Equity Restoration. *Marketing Letters*, 17(3), 155-172.
 31. Wijayanti, W., et al. (2023). Accessing Critical Information for Sports Event Stakeholders. *Journal of Information Systems in Sports*, 29(3), 201-218.
 32. Yang, J. (2014). Relevance and Accuracy of Sports Information. *Sports Information Review*, 27(1), 55-67.
 33. Hyatt, C. (2008). Enhancing Fan Experience Through Information Clarity. *Sports Marketing Quarterly*, 17(3), 112-120.